

History Enhanced Computing and Sustainability

Consent Form – online survey History-Enhanced Computing and Sustainability (HECaS).

This consent form will have been given to you with the Participant Information Sheet. Please ensure that you have read and understood the information contained in the Participant Information Sheet and asked any questions before you sign this form. If you have any questions please contact a member of the research team, whose details are set out on the Participant Information Sheet.

If you are happy to take part in this online survey, please click YES. You will be given a copy to keep for your records.

- I have read and understood the information in the Participant Information Sheet [Participant information sheet hecas v1.2](#) which I have been given to read before asked to sign this form;
- I have read and understood the Data Protection Privacy Notice [Research privacy notice hecas v1.0](#) that has been provided to me
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the study;
- I have had my questions answered satisfactorily by the research team;
- I agree that anonymised quotes may be used in the final Report of this study;
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time before the questionnaire has been completed, without giving a reason;
- I agree to take part in the research

Yes

No

What is your UWE email address? _____ (for matching before / after questionnaires. Data analysis will be anonymised.)

Q1 How relevant is a knowledge of history to your degree?

Very relevant

Somewhat relevant

Neutral

Somewhat irrelevant

Very irrelevant

Q2 How relevant is a knowledge of history to your career?

- Very relevant
 - Somewhat relevant
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat irrelevant
 - Very irrelevant
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Q3 How interested are you in history?

- Very interested
 - Somewhat interested
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat uninterested
 - Very uninterested
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Q4 What historical events are you aware of which are relevant to computing?
